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1 Introduction

The so-called “King’s Chamber” in the Great Pyramid is proclaimed as the final resting place of King Khufu, of the fourth dynasty in ancient Egypt. However, the only evidence we have for that is tenuous. The first “evidence” comes from the “Father of History / Father of Lies,” Herodotus, who wrote down what the Egyptian priests told him (*Histories* [3]), which is that Khufu built the great pyramid. This was more than 2000 years after Khufu’s reign, and after Egypt had endured much turmoil and conquest. The priests may have been sincere, but misinformed; or just protecting a lucrative business. Much can happen in 2000 years. Facts can get distorted or invented. Herodotus had a habit of mixing myth with facts [4], further complicating his accounts. The priests also said that Khufu was buried on an island underground, which means that the so-called “King’s Chamber” can not be Khufu’s final resting place. He also claimed that Khufu reigned after Ramesses II. Why do we cherry-pick only the parts we like?

The next pieces of “evidence” are the marks in the relieving chambers above the King’s Chamber, which were discovered by Howard Vyse (*Operations carried on at the pyramids of Gizeh in 1837: with an account of a voyage into Upper Egypt, and an appendix* [5]). Other investigators (*The Great Pyramid Hoax* [6], *Giza: The Fall of Dogma* [7]) have pointed out the problems with these marks, and why the important ones are fake. This paper will also prove that they are fake, by proving that the King’s Chamber can not be 4th dynasty.

Lastly, Merer’s diaries (*The Harbor of Khufu on the Red Sea Coast at Wadi al-Jarf* [8]) prove that Khufu did have a building project at Giza, referred to as the “Horizon of Khufu.” Experts assume that this means the great pyramid, yet the “Horizon of Akhenaten” at Tel el-Amarna does not refer to any pyramid that Akhenaten built. Perhaps Khufu just built a palace or temple, or did renovations to the pyramid (*The Diary Of Merer Tells Us NOTHING About the Great Pyramid’s Construction* [9]).

The so-called “Workers’ Village” (*Workers’ Town and Cemetery* [10]), which is frequently cited as proof that the pyramid was built by a skilled and cared-for labour force, dates to after Khufu (*Workers’ Town and Cemetery* [10]), and was clearly too small for the labour force required (*Labor and the Pyramids: The Heit el-Ghurab “Workers Town” at Giza* [11]) to extract and install one block every five minutes (*Construction of the Egyptian pyramids* [12]). So it more likely housed activities related to the port and looking after sailors, tourists and pilgrims, rather than a pyramid labour force.

This paper will show that the odds of the walls being random is so unlikely that it is easier to accept that the patterns were deliberately designed. That raises the questions of by whom, and when. I will show, by imposing increasingly stringent requirements on the design, that there is only one possible arrangement that meets them all, despite there being trillions of other ways of building the walls.

The thesis is thus that the walls of the King’s Chamber were not random, but deliberately designed, allowing well-known mathematical constants to be read off the walls. Thus it is definitely a “Chamber of Numbers,” and perhaps a burial chamber. This is a puzzle hidden in plain sight, for those that have eyes, to see.

Some citations are to Wikipedia pages, which provide a useful if non-authoritative summary for non-controversial topics.

1.1 Version history

1. 0.9.draft 23 September 2025 Draft version, while the permutation calculations are running.
2. 1.0.0 1 March 2026 First version.

1.2 Symbols and values

Giza is a construction site, so we are doing engineering, not pure mathematics, and thus $1.999 = 2.0$.

We will be using integer fractions to approximate various irrational constants, which by definition cannot be expressed as simple fractions. We can, however, approximate them to various levels of accuracy with fractions. Well-known examples are π approximated as $\frac{22}{7}$, or $\sqrt{2}$ as $\frac{99}{70}$.

Table 1 shows important numbers and their values typically used at Giza.

Symbol	Name	“Full” value	Typical Giza values
π	Archimedes’ constant	3.141592653...	3.14 or 3.142 or 3.1416 or 3.14159
$\frac{\pi}{2}$	Half π	1.570796326...	1.57 or 1.571
e	Euler’s number	2.718281828...	2.72 or 2.718 or 2.7183
φ	Golden ratio	1.618033988...	1.618 $\varphi + 1 = \varphi^2 = 2.618$
$\sqrt{2}$	Root 2	1.414213562...	1.414 or 1.4142
$\sqrt{\pi}$	Root π	1.772453851...	1.772 or 1.7725
$\ln(\pi)$	Natural log of 3.142	1.144859540 ...	1.1449
☉	Royal cubit	0.5236 m	0.5236 m

Table 1: Symbols, names and values

Our eyes are very sensitive to decimals, influenced by our education. We may see 3.14 or 3.142 or 3.1416 as π , but do we as easily see 1.62, or numbers that round to that, as φ ? Similarly, do we automatically see 2.72, or numbers that round to that, as e ? Again, this is engineering, not pure mathematics.

2 Large numbers and odds

We will be dealing with large numbers. There are at least two contradictory systems [13] for naming these, and most of the English-speaking world has, for better or worse, settled on the short system. The necessary names and values are shown in Table 2.

10^x	Name	Value	Metric name
10^6	Million	1,000,000	mega
10^9	Billion	1,000,000,000	giga
10^{12}	Trillion	1,000,000,000,000	tera
10^{15}	Quadrillion	1,000,000,000,000,000	peta
10^{18}	Quintillion	1,000,000,000,000,000,000	exa
10^{21}	Sextillion	1,000,000,000,000,000,000,000	zetta
10^{24}	Septillion	1,000,000,000,000,000,000,000,000	yotta

Table 2: Names for large numbers

As a way of putting these large numbers in context, Table 3 shows some examples.

Humans are very bad at dealing with large numbers. If you think that the number of ways to arrange 26 letters is large, try a standard deck of 52 playing cards (*52 Factorial* [14]). It is too large to include in full in one line in Table 3.

We will be looking at the probability of the wall design being random, and of the designers “getting lucky,” so Table 4 shows the chance of winning some competitions. The reader will note that these numbers are much smaller than those shown in Table 3.

Name	Value
Billion	1,000,000,000
Trillion	1,000,000,000,000
Number of cells in the human body	37,200,000,000,000
USA Federal debt, February 2026	38,800,000,000,000
Quadrillion	1,000,000,000,000,000
One parsec, to the nearest metre	30,856,775,814,913,673
Age of universe in seconds	435,500,000,000,000,000
Quintillion	1,000,000,000,000,000,000
Standard 3x3x3 Rubik's Cube possible combinations	43,252,003,274,489,856,000
Sextillion	1,000,000,000,000,000,000,000
Stars in observable universe (estimated)	50,000,000,000,000,000,000,000
Septillion	1,000,000,000,000,000,000,000,000
Ways to arrange 26 letters (26!)	403,291,461,126,605,635,584,000,000

Table 3: Examples of large numbers in context

Name	Odds
Odds of winning the South African Powerball main prize	1 : 42,375,200
Odds of winning the UK Lotto main prize	1 : 45,057,473
Odds of winning the EuroMillions main prize	1 : 139,838,160
Odds of winning the USA Powerball main prize	1 : 292,201,338

Table 4: Chances of winning

3 Number bases

In order to discuss a “Chamber of Numbers,” the first thing we need to clarify is which base we are using. Today, the vast majority of the world uses a base 10 number system, with value-by-position, and a special symbol for zero. In the past, different cultures had different systems, a few of which are listed in Table 5.

Name	Bases	Positional	Zero indicated	Zero as digit	Approximate date
Sumerian numerals	10 & 60	Yes	Yes	No	3100 BCE
Egyptian numerals	10	No	No	No	3000 BCE
Babylonian numerals	10 & 60	Yes	Yes	No	2000 BCE
Maya numerals	5 & 20	Yes	No	Yes	<15th Century

Table 5: Selected number bases

Modern computing languages use at least three bases, while some West African communities use duodecimal or dozenal, which is in fact superior to base 10. These are shown in Table 6.

Name	Base	Symbols	123_{10}	π
Binary	2	0 1	1111011	11.001001000011...
Octal	8	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7	173	3.1103755242102...
Duodecimal (dozenal)	12	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 ζ ξ	$\zeta 3$	3.184809493 ξ 918...
Hexadecimal	16	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 A B C D E F	7B	3.243F6A8885A3...

Table 6: Other notable number bases

The last two columns in Table 6 shows how very differently the same number is represented in different bases. So the first task of anyone trying to transmit numbers across time or culture, is to establish which base they are working in. The King's Chamber designer did this for us.

Figure 1 shows a diagram of of the King's Chamber, laid out flat. It is based on the original diagram by Charles Piazzi Smyth (*Life and Work at the Great Pyramid During the Months of January, February, March, and April, A.d. 1865: With a Discussion of the Facts Ascertained* [15]), with the block sizes based on his measurements, and those of Ingles. There is sadly no coherent set of accurate measurements of the blocks that I know of. Petrie measured the top row (once, it seems, unlike his usual method of nine times), and the bottom row of the north wall for a friend, but only published the top row figures. Appendix A contains a comparison of various measurements that I have found over the years.

The entrance is the dark block at the bottom right on the north wall.

Figure 1: The King's Chamber

There are several things to note about the walls.

1. There are currently exactly 100 blocks on the walls.
2. When the chamber was still sealed, there would have been 101 blocks, but the sealing block has vanished. As such, the space provides a zero.
3. The block at the bottom left corner of the west wall is slightly smaller than its space, suggesting that it can be removed. See the the gap along the top, and the modern mortar filling the gap on the right edge, in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The SW corner block. Picture credit: Larry Pahl

This block is thus considered 'variable,' sometimes counted, and sometimes not, as the need arises.

4. Each wall contains a multiple of 9 blocks, except the west wall, which has the extra variable block to bring the total up to 100. You can't make 100 by just using multiples of 9.
5. The minimum number of blocks in a row on a wall is 1, with a maximum of 10 on the long walls, and 5 on the short walls.
6. There is a double-row block over the entrance. This security feature also provides mathematical functions.
7. The block patterns appear random or haphazard, unlike modern brick walls.
8. The blocks are large. Each row is about 4 feet (47 inches) high (*The pyramids and temples of Gizeh* [16]). They are precisely fitted together, and it is clear that the masons could make a block in any desired size.

9. The longest blocks are at the top. This is counter-intuitive, but the reasons why will become clear shortly.
10. There is only one row with two blocks, at the top of the north wall. Again, the reason why will become clear shortly.

The design gives us clues as to which base to use: a minimum of one block in a row, a maximum of ten, and a total of 100, pointing to a base 10 system.

100	10	1
1	3	7

Table 7: A number in base 10

4 The 100

The key question we need to answer about the walls is, did the masons simply take the granite blocks received from Aswan, and randomly cut them to build the courses, or did they work according to a specific plan? Whether this includes the sizes and order of individual blocks, as well as the number per row, I do not know. Given how “everything” about Giza is designed, it is likely that individual block sizes were deliberate, but that puzzles yet eludes me.

If we assume the construction was random, then, for a minimum of one block per row per wall, and a maximum of ten, the number of different ways the walls could have been built is 10^{20} . For these calculations, I am treating the large block on the north wall as if it was in only one row. Also, we are not concerned with the order of the blocks in a row. Including that option would make the numbers even higher.

However, the shorter west and east walls have a maximum of five blocks in a row. If we use this constraint, then the number of possible ways drops considerably to $5^5 \times 10^5 \times 5^5 \times 10^5$ which is 97,656,250,000,000,000. Table 8 shows these two numbers in context.

Item	Value
Quadrillion	1,000,000,000,000,000
Ways to build the King’s Chamber walls, $5^5 \times 10^5 \times 5^5 \times 10^5$	97,656,250,000,000,000
Age of universe in seconds	435,500,000,000,000,000
Quintillion	1,000,000,000,000,000,000
Standard 3x3x3 Rubik’s Cube possible combinations	43,252,003,274,489,856,000
Ways to build the King’s Chamber walls, 10^{20}	100,000,000,000,000,000,000
Sextillion	1,000,000,000,000,000,000,000
Stars in observable universe (estimated)	50,000,000,000,000,000,000,000

Table 8: Reduced combinations in context

These combinations include all values from a total of 20 blocks (one per row per wall) up to 150 (25 + 50 + 25 + 50). However, we have a limit of 100 blocks in total, so the question is, how many of these 97 quadrillion combinations are exactly 100 blocks? I could not find a statistician to help me, so I tried the so-called “Artificial Intelligence” services. At the time, they all gave wildly varying answers, none of which turned out to be correct.

So I did it the hard way, using programs. I broke the problem into 25 chunks, and set my computer to work on the first 13. After about 3 months, I bought a new, faster computer, and let it do the other 12 chunks. The old computer ran for about 4 months, the new computer for about 2 months.

During this time, Google Gemini added a proper maths engine and was able to answer the question. I left my programs running to see if they got the same answer, which they did.

The programs checked a total of 97,656,250,000,000,000 possible combinations, and found 1,309,073,629,685,518 with exactly 100 blocks. So the hit rate was about 1.34%.

4.1 Multiples of 9

To further reduce the possibilities, we introduce the next restriction, which is that each wall is a multiple of 9 blocks. Again, we treat the single big block as if it was in only one row. There is a further restriction, in that the extra block has to go on the west wall. This is because both the King’s Chamber, and the Giza site plan,

are double squares, and there are hints that they are connected. I do not fully understand the connection, but accept it and work with it.

Figure 3 shows the triple merge of the star map behind the Giza design, the Giza site plan (*Zep Tepi Mathematics 101*, [17]), and the King’s Chamber floor. Note how P1 (Khufu) matches up with the chamber entrance. P6 (Vega) matches with the location of the extra block on the west wall, even if the size does not correlate in the same way as the entrance and P1. For this reason, I suggest that the extra block, and its possible hidden entrance, has to go in that spot.

Figure 3: Triple merge of star map, Giza site plan, and King’s Chamber floor

Table 9 shows the 68 possible ways to have four walls, each with a multiple of 9 blocks, with the west wall having one extra block. That means the west wall could have 10, 19, 28, 37, or 46 blocks, and the other three walls could have 9, 18, 27, 36, or 45 blocks. Each cell contains a pattern in West-North-East-South order.

W N E S	W N E S	W N E S	W N E S	W N E S	W N E S
10 18 27 45	10 18 36 36	10 18 45 27	10 27 18 45	10 27 45 18	10 36 18 36
10 36 36 18	10 36 45 9	10 36 9 45	10 45 18 27	10 45 27 18	10 45 36 9
10 45 9 36	10 9 36 45	10 9 45 36	19 18 18 45	19 18 27 36	19 18 36 27
19 18 45 18	19 27 18 36	19 27 27 27	19 27 36 18	19 27 45 9	19 27 9 45
19 36 18 27	19 36 27 18	19 36 36 9	19 36 9 36	19 45 18 18	19 45 27 9
19 45 9 27	19 9 27 45	19 9 36 36	19 9 45 27	28 18 18 36	28 18 27 27
28 18 36 18	28 18 45 9	28 18 9 45	28 27 18 27	28 27 27 18	28 36 18 18
28 45 18 9	28 45 9 18	28 9 18 45	28 9 45 18	37 18 18 27	37 18 27 18
37 18 36 9	37 18 9 36	37 27 18 18	37 36 18 9	37 36 9 18	37 45 9 9
37 9 18 36	37 9 36 18	37 9 45 9	37 9 9 45	46 18 18 18	46 18 27 9
46 18 9 27	46 27 18 9	46 27 9 18	46 36 9 9	46 9 18 27	46 9 27 18
46 9 36 9	46 9 9 36				

Table 9: Possible ways to arrange the walls

However, we need to be practical. Putting 45 or 46 blocks on one wall uses up almost half of the 100 blocks, and there would need to be an average of 9 blocks in each row. So those options are not viable. Likewise, using only 9 or 10 blocks spread across five rows means that each row would average about two blocks, again not very practical. Further, the short walls can only have a maximum of 25 blocks, so we can ignore any patterns that put more than 18 or 19 on the short walls.

Once we remove all the patterns meeting those conditions, we are left with exactly two, as shown in Table 10.

These are essentially the same pattern, it just depends which way you go around the room, as north and south are swapped.

W	N	E	S
19	27	18	36
19	36	18	27

Table 10: The only ways to arrange the walls

The north wall, and its double block, has to get the 27 blocks, as the patterns that we will shortly show will not work if we put the 36 blocks on the north wall.

4.2 How many ways to build a wall?

Now that we know how many blocks go on each wall, we need to know how to arrange them. There are many different ways to build each wall, as shown in Table 11. These values were determined via programs that generated all possibilities for each wall, and checked if the total number of bricks for the wall was correct. From this point on, we treat the big block on the north wall as if half was in row 3, and half in row 4.

Item	West	North	East	South
Number of blocks	19	27	18	36
Number of ways	175	5006	255	2710

Table 11: Ways the walls could have been built

That gives us $175 \times 5006 \times 255 \times 2710 = 605,394,352,502$ ways that the 100 blocks could have been arranged on the four walls. For ease of future reference, I shall refer to this as *Nefi's number*.

Nefi's number is also interesting. Its prime factors are 2, 61, 19 and 261,170,989. We note the subtle nods to 2.618, and the large prime.

Table 12 shows that number in context.

Name	Value
Million	1,000,000
Odds of winning the EuroMillions main prize, 1 in	139,838,160
Odds of winning the USA Powerball main prize, 1 in	292,201,338
Billion	1,000,000,000
Ways the 19 - 27 - 18 - 36 walls could have been built	605,394,352,502
Trillion	1,000,000,000,000

Table 12: The possible block combinations in context

Table 13 shows some samples of these combinations, with the row counts from top to bottom shown from left to right.

West	North	East	South
1 3 5 5 5	1 1 5.5 9.5 10	1 2 5 5 5	1 10 10 10 5
1 4 4 5 5	1 1 6.5 8.5 10	1 3 4 5 5	1 10 10 5 10
1 4 5 4 5	1 1 7.5 7.5 10	1 3 5 4 5	1 10 10 6 9
1 4 5 5 4	1 1 6.5 9.5 9	1 3 5 5 4	1 10 10 7 8
1 5 3 5 5	1 1 7.5 8.5 9	1 4 3 5 5	1 10 10 8 7
1 5 4 4 5	1 1 8.5 6.5 10	1 4 4 4 5	1 10 10 9 6

Table 13: Sample block patterns on the four walls

5 The King's Chamber Game

The King's Chamber can be viewed as a set of puzzles. Some puzzles are relatively easy, as a way to get us started, like π at 3.142 or $\sqrt{2}$ at 1.414. Others are more complex like π at 3.14159265358979 or φ at 1.6180339887. I say "relatively easy," because the first puzzle, π at 3.142, is easy but none of the numerous experts, or millions of ordinary tourists, noticed it (as far as I know) until it was shown to me.

Table 14: Different skill levels required

The King’s Chamber Game (*The Writing is on the Wall: The King’s Chamber Game* [1]) is a game I was shown, played with the block patterns on the walls. All you have to do is count the blocks in different ways.

Some basic rules or guidelines:

- Use whole rows at a time. There are two exceptions for this. Firstly, the bottom row on the west wall has the variable block, so we can optionally use 4 or 5 here. Secondly, the 3rd and 4th row on the north wall has the big block, which can be used or ignored, treated alone, or taken as forcing both rows to be used as a unit.
- Rows can be counted together, preferably adjacent rows where possible.
- The digits which the row represents can be strung together or added. For example, the two top rows on the west wall are one and four. We can read this as the string 14 or add them together to get 5. Going from the bottom up, we could get 41 instead of 14. Remember it is a game or puzzle where you need to find the hidden patterns.
- The decimal point is for the player to insert. This is similar to using a slide rule.

5.1 The horizontal patterns

The next step in narrowing the number of ways that the walls could have been built, is to point out that we can easily read π , φ , φ^2 , and e from the walls and floor, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Famous irrationals on the walls and floor of the King’s Chamber

I wrote a program that generated all 605,394,352,502 combinations, and then checked each one to see if

1. The first two rows had 31 blocks
2. The third and fourth rows had 42 blocks
3. At least one wall had a row of 10 blocks in the bottom row.

The other arithmetic conditions are done automatically.

Of the 605,394,352,502 possibilities, 569,219,916 combinations met those three requirements. That is about 1 in 1064 of Nefi’s Number.

5.2 The vertical patterns

We then check how many of those also allow the main vertical patterns shown in Figure 5, or a version of them, to be done.

Figure 5: The main vertical patterns

For this, the requirements are less precise than with the horizontal patterns.

There are limited ways to make each number. For 1.414 with 19 blocks, you need some combination of 1, 4 and 14. So we limit the west wall to be 1 4 ? ? ? or ? ? ? 1 4.

The north wall must either be 2 7 18, or 27 1 8 or 27 18. However, there are only 27 blocks on the wall, so the only viable pattern is 2 7 18. So we limit results for the north wall to those that have 2 and 7 in the first two rows. We can't spread the 7 over two rows because of the big block.

The east wall must follow a 1 5 ? ? ? pattern.

Lastly, the south wall must be 3 ? ? ? ? and the second and third rows must add up to 14. This is also the reason why the 36 block wall can not incorporate the big block and must thus be the southern wall. It can't be 3 1 4 ? ? because there is no way to get a total of 36 like that.

There are only 433 combinations that also meet this requirement. The number 433 is interesting, as $433 \times 4 = 1732$, which is $1000\sqrt{3}$.

Further, if we divide the possibilities from the previous round by 433, we get $\frac{569,219,916}{433} = 1,314,595.649$. We note that the first six digits of that, 131459, is an anagram of π at 3.14159.

Compared to Nefi's Number, 433 ways is a 1 in 1,398,139,382 lucky shot if it was random. That is less likely than winning the USA Powerball four times.

In case the reader is wondering about putting the numbers on different walls, other combinations do not work. For example, 1.414 is a natural fit for the wall with nineteen blocks. If you wanted to do it on the east wall which has 18 blocks, the only way is 1 - 4 - 1 and then two rows which add up to 4, but that would immediately break the horizontal patterns in Figure 4. You cannot get the total of 18 like that either. That forces 1.414 to the west wall. It is impossible to do 2.718 on the east wall, so it has to be on the north or south wall. Trying to do 3 - 1 - 4 - 1 - 5 - 9 on the north wall runs into problems with the double block, and the horizontal patterns, so π has to go on the south wall. That puts e on the north wall, and $\frac{\pi}{2}$ on the east wall.

5.3 The square root of 10π

We then check how many of those 433 possibilities also allow us to get $\sqrt{10\pi}$ using unit fractions as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Rows are unit fractions

This calculation works by treating the number of blocks in each row as the denominator in a unit fraction. The only special case is the double row on the north wall, where the big block is used as an indicator to combine the two rows. (Or, the big block is 1 and the rest is 10.)

These fractions add up to $5\frac{305}{504}$, which is 5.605 to three decimals. $5.605^2 = 31.416$ to three places. ($\sqrt{10\pi}$ on Khufu's King's Chamber Walls [2])

We do this unit fraction calculation with each of the 433 possibilities, and check which give 5.605 rounded. That reduces the possibilities down to only 84.

Some sample results of this round are shown in Table 15. See Appendix B for all 84.

West	North	East	South
1 4 4 5 5	2 7 8.5 2.5 7	1 5 4 3 5	3 8 6 9 10
1 4 4 5 5	2 7 9.5 1.5 7	1 5 3 4 5	3 8 6 9 10
1 4 4 5 5	2 7 9.5 1.5 7	1 5 4 3 5	3 8 6 9 10
1 4 5 4 5	2 7 1.5 6.5 10	1 5 4 5 3	3 8 6 10 9
1 4 5 4 5	2 7 1.5 6.5 10	1 5 5 4 3	3 8 6 10 9
1 4 5 4 5	2 7 2.5 5.5 10	1 5 4 5 3	3 8 6 10 9
1 4 5 4 5	2 7 2.5 5.5 10	1 5 5 4 3	3 8 6 10 9
1 4 5 4 5	2 7 1.5 9.5 7	1 5 3 4 5	3 8 6 9 10
1 4 5 4 5	2 7 1.5 9.5 7	1 5 4 3 5	3 8 6 9 10
1 4 5 4 5	2 7 2.5 8.5 7	1 5 3 4 5	3 8 6 9 10

Table 15: Sample block patterns on the four walls

Considering the 84 ways against Nefi's Number, it is a 1 in 7,207,075,625 probability.

5.4 π to 14 decimal places

Next, we note that the chamber as built allows us to read π correct to 14 decimal places, and $\frac{\pi}{2}$ to 3 decimal places, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: π and π/2 on the walls of the King's Chamber

Pi to 14 digits consists of the digits 1 1 2 3 3 4 5 5 5 6 7 8 9 **9 9**. The digits in bold are made up from two rows, while the rest are single rows.

The leftover blocks give us 1 7 **15**. These are the digits for half π , which acts as a confirmation that what we are doing is correct.

NASA only needs to use 15 digits for π . Using more digits than that provides only marginal improvement in accuracy at the edge of the solar system [18].

I manually checked which of the remaining 84 arrangements provide these digits. For this, we treat the large block as if it was in its own row. That left us with 12 possible arrangements, shown in Table 16

West	North	East	South
1 4 4 5 5	2 7 1.5 9.5 7	1 5 3 4 5	3 8 6 9 10
1 4 4 5 5	2 7 1.5 9.5 7	1 5 4 3 5	3 8 6 9 10
1 4 4 5 5	2 7 5.5 5.5 7	1 5 3 4 5	3 8 6 9 10
1 4 4 5 5	2 7 5.5 5.5 7	1 5 4 3 5	3 8 6 9 10
1 4 4 5 5	2 7 9.5 1.5 7	1 5 3 4 5	3 8 6 9 10
1 4 4 5 5	2 7 9.5 1.5 7	1 5 4 3 5	3 8 6 9 10
1 4 5 4 5	2 7 1.5 9.5 7	1 5 3 4 5	3 8 6 9 10
1 4 5 4 5	2 7 1.5 9.5 7	1 5 4 3 5	3 8 6 9 10
1 4 5 4 5	2 7 5.5 5.5 7	1 5 3 4 5	3 8 6 9 10
1 4 5 4 5	2 7 5.5 5.5 7	1 5 4 3 5	3 8 6 9 10
1 4 5 4 5	2 7 9.5 1.5 7	1 5 3 4 5	3 8 6 9 10
1 4 5 4 5	2 7 9.5 1.5 7	1 5 4 3 5	3 8 6 9 10

Table 16: Patterns allowing the digits of π and $\pi/2$ to be read off the walls

5.5 There can only be one

The designer had to pick one of these options. Which criteria should she use? Given the path that we have followed to get to these twelve, it is not unreasonable to expect further use of the same mathematical constants, from amongst π , φ , φ^2 , e or $\sqrt{2}$.

The south wall is already fixed at 3 8 6 9 10.

The west wall has two options: 1 4 4 5 5 or 1 4 5 4 5. We note that the first variant provides two Fibonacci numbers, 144 and 55, and that $\frac{144}{55}$ is 2.618, or φ^2 . The same order is necessary to do $\ln(\pi)$, shown in §8.6. So we choose 1 4 4 5 5 for the west wall.

The north wall has three options: 2 7 5.5 5.5 7, 2 7 1.5 9.5 7, or 2 7 9.5 1.5 7.

The options with 1.5 and 9.5 require that the north wall have a row with one block about 7 metres long, and another row with 9 blocks, averaging about 77cm long each. A block 7 metres long would be the longest in the chamber, and being adjacent to a row with nine blocks would look distinctly odd.

On the other hand, the combination with 5 blocks each in rows three and four, when read from the bottom, provides $\frac{755}{72}$, which is 10.486, and $\sqrt{\frac{10.486}{4}}$ is approximately (to 2 decimals) φ .

The east wall has two options, 1 5 4 3 5 or 1 5 3 4 5. The first of these, when read from the bottom, provides $\frac{534}{51}$, which is 10.4706, and $\sqrt{\frac{10.4706}{4}}$ is approximately (to 2 decimals) φ , similarly to the north wall.

Further, if we read the indicated north and east walls from the bottom, then we have $\frac{75572}{53451}$ which is 1.414 to three decimals, or $\sqrt{2}$.

We thus select 1 4 4 5 5 for the west wall, 2 7 5.5 5.5 7 for the north wall, and 1 5 4 3 5 for the east wall, giving us the chamber as built, in Figure 8.

Figure 8: The Chamber of Numbers

6 Discussion

Let us recap how we got to the final design, and the numbers involved, as summarised in Table 17.

Item	Ways
1. Four walls, up to 10 blocks per row (10^{20})	100,000,000,000,000,000,000
2. Four walls, up to 5 (short walls) or 10 blocks per row ($5^5 \times 10^5 \times 5^5 \times 10^5$)	97,656,250,000,000,000
3. 100 blocks on four walls	1,309,073,629,685,518
4. 100 blocks, each wall is a multiple of 9 (Nefi's number)	605,394,352,502
5. Provides $\pi, \varphi, \varphi^2, e$ in horizontal patterns	569,219,916
6. Also provides $\sqrt{2}, e, \frac{\pi}{2}, \pi$ in vertical patterns	433
7. Also provides $\sqrt{10\pi}$	84
8. Also provides π to 14 decimals, and $\frac{\pi}{2}$ to 3 decimals	12
9. Also references φ, φ^2 and $\sqrt{2}$	1

Table 17: The final countdown

In order to determine how lucky the design is, we need to decide on our possible universe of options. I propose that option 1 in Table 17 is too generous, as putting up to ten blocks per row on the short walls means an average of 1 G , or about 52cm, per block, which is very narrow compared to the row height of 2.28 G. So the realistic starting points are options 2, 3 or 4.

I shall refer to Item 2 as “Large universe”, Item 3 as “Small universe,” and Item 4 as Nefi’s number.

We then need to decide at which point we consider the design requirements to stop. We can argue about whether this is after points 8 or 9 in Table 17. If we take point 8, then the odds of it being random in the Large universe is 1: 8,138,020,833,333,333.

On the other hand, if we consider our universe to be limited to 100 blocks, then we use the Small universe, and stopping after point 8 means the odds of it being random is 1 : 109,089,469,140,460.

If we consider our universe to be just one particular subset with 100 blocks, arranged with a multiple of 9 on each wall, then our universe is Nefi’s number, and stopping after point 8 means the odds of it being random is 1 : 50,449,529,375.

If we stopped at point 9, then the odds would be 1 in 97,656,250,000,000,000, 1 in 1,309,073,629,685,518, or 1 in 605,394,352,50, depending on our universe.

We put these numbers in context in Table 18.

Item	Odds
Odds of winning the South African Lotto main prize	1 : 20,358,520
Odds of winning the South African Powerball main prize	1 : 42,375,200
Odds of winning the UK Lotto main prize	1 : 45,057,473
Odds of winning the EuroMillions main prize	1 : 139,838,160
Odds of winning the USA Powerball main prize	1 : 292,201,338
Odds of winning Nefi's number after point 8	1 : 50,449,529,375
Odds of winning Nefi's number after point 9	1 : 605,394,352,502
Odds of winning Small universe after point 8	1 : 109,089,469,140,460
Odds of winning Small universe after point 9	1 : 1,309,073,629,685,518
Odds of winning Large universe after point 8	1 : 8,138,020,833,333,333
Odds of winning Large universe after point 9	1 : 97,656,250,000,000,000

Table 18: Winning odds in context

We propose that one of the highlighted odds, of 1 : Nefi's number, or 1 : Small universe, are the correct and reasonable odds of the wall patterns being random, even though they are not the least unlikely.

The chances of doing this by luck are still orders of magnitude less likely than winning the USA Powerball, and as such, it is extremely unlikely that the chamber, as built, was "Sheer Dumb Luck!" This means it must have been designed that way on purpose.

7 The elephant in the corner

It is all very well to point out how unlikely it is for the walls to be a random design. The reverse problem is much more difficult: how would the designer have come up with the design, if she had been given requirements 4 to 9 in Table 17? At which point would she have realised that she needed a double block, or tried to incorporate it, given that it is a security requirement?

The design brief may have been less specific, for example "Design the walls so that various mathematical constants can be read from the block patterns. You can choose which ones." We note that π and variations on π are favoured above all other numbers, as in the Giza site plan. Even the chamber dimensions point to π , as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: The cubit and metre relationship

8 Bonuses inherent in the design

It is possible that, instead of being designed from scratch, the chamber simply concretised (granitised?), or recorded for posterity, knowledge which had developed over time. This would be analogous to how the larger Giza design appears to bring together assorted observations on numbers, into one unified design (*The Consequences of Legon's Rectangle: The Rational Giza Design* [19], *Zep Tepi Mathematics 101* [17]).

8.1 Approximating $\sqrt{2}$ rationally

The walls give the famous approximation for $\sqrt{2}$, the fraction $\frac{99}{70}$. To do this, we treat the 3rd and 4th row as one, giving us four rows. This gives us the set-up as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Block counts for fractions

Then we read the rows as numerator, denominator, numerator, denominator, starting at the top, and the following regular pattern is true, starting at the bottom left:

$$\frac{\frac{9}{5} \times \frac{11}{7}}{\frac{7}{5} \times \frac{15}{10}} \div \frac{\frac{1}{4} \times \frac{2}{7}}{\frac{1}{5} \times \frac{3}{8}} = \frac{99}{70} \approx \sqrt{2}$$

8.2 $10 \times \frac{22}{7}$

The above example was done using our modern fraction notation. We write, for example, $\frac{3}{4}$ or 3/4, and read that as “take 3 parts of something divided into 4 parts.” A different culture would most likely have had a different way of denoting fractions, perhaps $\frac{4}{3}$, with or without a dividing line, or 4/3, and read that as “divide something into 4 parts, and take 3 of them.”

Either way, you still get the same 0.75 decimal value.

If we interpret the same fractions above the other way around, then we can read, after slightly rounding the second last step to integers,

$$\frac{4}{1} \times \frac{7}{2} \times \frac{5}{1} \times \frac{8}{3} \times \frac{5}{9} \times \frac{7}{11} \times \frac{5}{7} \times \frac{10}{15} = \frac{28000}{891} = \frac{220}{7} = 10\pi$$

Is it not amazing how the same set of integers, set in stone for thousands of years, give both well-known rational approximations for $\sqrt{2}$ and $(10)\pi$?

8.3 φ to 10 places

The walls give φ to 10 places. We ignore the optional block on the west wall, and use the entrance as a zero, as shown in Figure 11.

φ

Figure 11: φ to 10 places

This indicates at least the use of the Sumerian/Babylonian technique of “indicate zero,” to show a digit is missing, if not full use of the zero as a digit in its own right.

8.4 Powers of two

The powers of two can be read in boustrophedon fashion, as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: The powers of 2

8.5 Prime numbers

The first nine primes can be read, as shown in Figure 13. We note that 1 is not a prime number.

Figure 13: The primes

8.6 Five references to π

While the south and east walls give us π and $\frac{\pi}{2}$ (as previously shown in Figure 5), the north wall gives us both $\sqrt{\pi}$ and π^2 . The west wall, together with the large block, gives us the remarkable natural logarithm $\ln(3.142)$, correct to four decimals.

Figure 14: Multiple versions of π

For π^2 , we read the blocks on the north wall from the bottom up, giving us either $\frac{710}{72}$ or $\frac{711}{72}$, depending on whether you want to include the big block or not. That equates to 9.8611 and 9.875 respectively, and the square roots of those are 3.14 and 3.142 respectively.

Having $\ln(3.142)$ here takes things to a whole different level.

8.7 π with a zero

Figure 15: More π , with a zero

As opposed to the vertical patterns in Figure 14, Figure 15 uses horizontal patterns read from the right edge, including zero as a digit. We again exclude the variable block on the west wall.

9 Conclusion

There are trillions or quadrillions of ways that they could have built the walls in the King's Chamber, yet only a handful allow certain mathematical constants to be read from the walls at the same time.

These constants include:

- π at 3.142, 3.14159, 3.1420, and 3.14159265358979
- $\frac{\pi}{2}$ at 1.57 and 1.571
- $\sqrt{\pi}$ at 1.772 and 17725
- $\sqrt{10\pi}$ at $5\frac{305}{504}$ (= 5.605) via unit fractions

- 10π at $10 \times \frac{22}{7}$ via fractions
- π^2 at $\frac{710}{72}$ or $\frac{711}{72}$ (3.14^2 and 3.142^2) via fractions
- $\ln(\pi)$ at 1.1449
- φ at 1.618 and 1.6180339887
- φ^2 at 2.618
- e at 2.718
- $\sqrt{2}$ at 1.414
- $\sqrt{2}$ at $\frac{99}{70}$ via fractions

As such, we argue that the walls were built that way deliberately.

However, the 4th dynasty almost certainly did not have any concept of π (*Controversial History of Pi in Ancient Egypt, Old Babylonia, and Ancient Greek Mathematics* [20]), let alone φ or e . They could do calculations involving circles, but in a different way, and with an implied value for π of around 3.16, or $\sqrt{10}$ [20].

Milo Gardener [21] points out (pers. corr.) that the Ahmes (Rhind) mathematical papyrus [22] does indicate a process where they corrected previous calculations involving payments in grain, effectively resulting in an implied π value of $\frac{22}{7}$. As I understand it, this still implies that they still did not have the concept of π , as the fixed ratio between a circle's circumference and diameter, but realised that their original calculations needed correcting.

How then is it possible that these numbers can be read, not just once, but in several different ways, and in varying degrees of precision? Was it all just "Sheer dumb luck!"?

Occam's Razor would suggest that it is not luck, but design, and if the 4th dynasty did not know these numbers, then it must have been a different culture that built that room, and by implication, the great pyramid.

We do not know of any succeeding dynasty displaying knowledge of π or φ until the Persian and Greek periods. Even then, the value of π was only $\frac{22}{7}$, not more precise. As for e , it was not discovered until the 1600s CE in Europe.

If it was not after the 4th dynasty, then it must have been before. However, once again we have no record of any other culture with this knowledge. The only rational conclusion is that the King's Chamber was built by a culture currently lost to history, with no record except for their impressive pyramids, and hidden messages left in the universal language of mathematics.

The King's Chamber Game only works because the patterns work in a base ten positional system. The dynastic Egyptians did not use such a system. If the King's Chamber Game is valid, then the chamber can not be 4th dynasty. By implication, Vyse faked the marks in the relieving chambers.

Our histories of settled human culture in Egypt do not go back earlier than the Younger Dryas (*Younger Dryas* [24]), and if we have no record of a sufficiently advanced culture after the Younger Dryas, then it must have been before that.

Göbekli Tepe and other Taş Tepeler (*Taş Tepeler* [25]) sites in Türkiye show that cultures capable of working stone "in the large" existed circa 9500 BCE. Such skills, and the required tools, do not develop overnight.

Did these skills develop after the Younger Dryas, or survive from an earlier time?

"Contradictions do not exist. Whenever you think that you are facing a contradiction, check your premises. You will find that one of them is wrong."

Ayn Rand

10 Appendix A: Block sizes

These measurements of the walls were collected over the years. Not all are publicly available.

The originals were in various units, being old British inches, modern British inches, and metric, but with varying degrees of accuracy. They ranged between a quarter or half inch or centimetre, to Petrie-level precision. I converted them all to millimetres for comparison.

Sources:

1. Ingles and Smyth: *Life and Work at the Great Pyramid During the Months of January, February, March, and April, A.d. 1865: With a Discussion of the Facts Ascertained* [15]
2. Bannon and Bannon 2: private papers of the late Hugh Patrick Bannon [26], sent to Larry Pahl [27], and shared with me.
3. Petrie: *The pyramids and temples of Gizeh* [16]
4. Dormion: *La chambre de Chéops : analyse architecturale / Gilles Dormion* [28]
5. Benjamin: *NEC SecretSymbol Presentation PDF | PDF | Triangle | Geometry* [29]

Figure 16: Measurements of north and east walls

South Wall

West Wall

Figure 17: Measurements of south and west walls

11 Appendix B: The last 84 possibilities

West	North	East	South	West	North	East	South
14455	271.56.510	15453	386109	14545	274.53.510	15453	386109
14455	271.56.510	15543	386109	14545	274.53.510	15543	386109
14455	272.55.510	15453	386109	14545	274.56.57	15345	386910
14455	272.55.510	15543	386109	14545	274.56.57	15435	386910
14455	271.59.57	15345	386910	14545	275.52.510	15453	386109
14455	271.59.57	15435	386910	14545	275.52.510	15543	386109
14455	272.58.57	15345	386910	14545	275.55.57	15345	386910
14455	272.58.57	15435	386910	14545	275.55.57	15435	386910
14455	273.54.510	15453	386109	14545	276.51.510	15453	386109
14455	273.54.510	15543	386109	14545	276.51.510	15543	386109
14455	273.57.57	15345	386910	14545	276.54.57	15345	386910
14455	273.57.57	15435	386910	14545	276.54.57	15435	386910
14455	274.53.510	15453	386109	14545	277.53.57	15345	386910
14455	274.53.510	15543	386109	14545	277.53.57	15435	386910
14455	274.56.57	15345	386910	14545	278.52.57	15345	386910
14455	274.56.57	15435	386910	14545	278.52.57	15435	386910
14455	275.52.510	15453	386109	14545	279.51.57	15345	386910
14455	275.52.510	15543	386109	14545	279.51.57	15435	386910
14455	275.55.57	15345	386910	14554	271.56.510	15354	386109
14455	275.55.57	15435	386910	14554	271.56.510	15453	386910
14455	276.51.510	15453	386109	14554	271.56.510	15534	386109
14455	276.51.510	15543	386109	14554	271.56.510	15543	386910
14455	276.54.57	15345	386910	14554	272.55.510	15354	386109
14455	276.54.57	15435	386910	14554	272.55.510	15453	386910
14455	277.53.57	15345	386910	14554	272.55.510	15534	386109
14455	277.53.57	15435	386910	14554	272.55.510	15543	386910
14455	278.52.57	15345	386910	14554	273.54.510	15354	386109
14455	278.52.57	15435	386910	14554	273.54.510	15453	386910
14455	279.51.57	15345	386910	14554	273.54.510	15534	386109
14455	279.51.57	15435	386910	14554	273.54.510	15543	386910
14545	271.56.510	15453	386109	14554	274.53.510	15354	386109
14545	271.56.510	15543	386109	14554	274.53.510	15453	386910
14545	272.55.510	15453	386109	14554	274.53.510	15534	386109
14545	272.55.510	15543	386109	14554	274.53.510	15543	386910
14545	271.59.57	15345	386910	14554	275.52.510	15354	386109
14545	271.59.57	15435	386910	14554	275.52.510	15453	386910
14545	272.58.57	15345	386910	14554	275.52.510	15534	386109
14545	272.58.57	15435	386910	14554	275.52.510	15543	386910
14545	273.54.510	15453	386109	14554	276.51.510	15354	386109
14545	273.54.510	15543	386109	14554	276.51.510	15453	386910
14545	273.57.57	15345	386910	14554	276.51.510	15534	386109
14545	273.57.57	15435	386910	14554	276.51.510	15543	386910

Table 19: The final 84 possibilities

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Bibliography

- [1] I. Douglas, 'The Writing is on the Wall: The King's Chamber Game', Zenodo, 2022-05-22. Accessed: 2022-07-19. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6570342>.
- [2] I. Douglas, '√10π on Khufu's King's Chamber Walls', Zenodo, 2023-08-15. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8249702. Accessed: 2023-09-13. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/record/8249702>.
- [3] Herodotus, *Histories*, trans. by G. C. Macaulay. Standard Ebooks, 2025-07-08. Accessed: 2025-08-14. [Online]. Available: <https://standardebooks.org/ebooks/herodotus/histories/g-c-macaulay>.
- [4] '1. Introduction', The Center for Hellenic Studies, Accessed: 2025-08-14. [Online]. Available: <https://chs.harvard.edu/chapter/1-introduction-2/>.
- [5] R. W. H. Howard-Vyse and J. S. Perring, *Operations Carried on at the Pyramids of Gizeh in 1837: With an Account of a Voyage into Upper Egypt, and an Appendix*. London, J. Fraser, 1840, 406 pp. Accessed: 2021-09-18. [Online]. Available: <http://archive.org/details/operationscarrie01howa>.
- [6] *The Great Pyramid Hoax*. 2016-12-15, ISBN: 978-1-59143-789-5. Accessed: 2023-11-07. [Online]. Available: <https://www.simonandschuster.com/books/The-Great-Pyramid-Hoax/Scott-Creighton/9781591437895>.
- [7] A. de'Flumeri, G. Montuschi and A. Tavecchia, *Giza: The Fall of Dogma*. Luca Montuschi, 494 pp., ISBN: 978-1-968296-06-3.
- [8] G. Marouard and P. Tallet, 'THE HARBOR OF KHUFU on the Red Sea Coast at Wadi al-Jarf, Egypt (NEA 77/1)', Accessed: 2023-10-28. [Online]. Available: https://www.academia.edu/6248978/THE_HARBOR_OF_KHUFU_on_the_Red_Sea_Coast_at_Wadi_al_Jarf_Egypt_NEA_77_1.
- [9] Ancient Architects, director, *The Diary Of Merer Tells Us NOTHING About the Great Pyramid's Construction*, 2025-09-19. Accessed: 2025-09-20. [Online]. Available: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5qPvK64bG1o>.
- [10] 'Workers' Town and Cemetery', Accessed: 2025-08-05. [Online]. Available: <https://egymonuments.gov.eg/en/monuments/workers-town-and-cemetery/>.
- [11] M. Lehner, 'Labor and the Pyramids: The Heit el-Ghurab "Workers Town" at Giza', in 2015-01-01, pp. 397–522, ISBN: 978-3-9814842-3-6.
- [12] *Construction of the Egyptian pyramids*, in *Wikipedia*, 2025-08-10. Accessed: 2025-08-17. [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Construction_of_the_Egyptian_pyramids&oldid=1305146190.
- [13] *Long and short scales*, in *Wikipedia*, 2025-08-12. Accessed: 2025-08-12. [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Long_and_short_scales&oldid=1305420719.
- [14] '52 Factorial', Accessed: 2025-08-25. [Online]. Available: https://czep.net/weblog/52cards.html?source=post_page-----4f3dad23ce01-----.
- [15] C. P. (P. Smyth, *Life and Work at the Great Pyramid During the Months of January, February, March, and April, A.d. 1865: With a Discussion of the Facts Ascertained*. Edinburgh, Edmonston and Douglas, 1867, 544 pp. Accessed: 2022-07-19. [Online]. Available: <http://archive.org/details/lifeworkatgreatp02smytuoft>.
- [16] W. M. F. (M. F. Petrie, *The Pyramids and Temples of Gizeh*. London : Field & Tuer ; New York : Scribner & Welford, 1883, 315 pp. Accessed: 2021-09-18. [Online]. Available: <http://archive.org/details/cu31924012038927>.
- [17] I. Douglas, 'Zep Tepi Mathematics 101', Zenodo, 2021-01-16. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4410650. Accessed: 2021-09-18. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4410650>.
- [18] 'How Many Decimals of Pi Do We Really Need? - Edu News', NASA/JPL Edu, Accessed: 2023-11-28. [Online]. Available: <https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/edu/news/2016/3/16/how-many-decimals-of-pi-do-we-really-need/>.
- [19] I. Douglas, 'The Consequences of Legon's Rectangle: The Rational Giza Design', Zenodo, 2022-10-16. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7213357. Accessed: 2023-08-13. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/record/7213357>.
- [20] J. Park, 'Controversial History of Pi in Ancient Egypt, Old Babylonia, and Ancient Greek Mathematics', *Journal for History of Mathematics*, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 223–236, 2020, ISSN: 1226-931X. DOI: 10.14477/jhm.2020.33.4.223. Accessed: 2021-10-08. [Online]. Available: <https://www.koreascience.or.kr/article/JAKO202026252145000.page>.
- [21] m. gardner. '(99+) milo gardner - Independent Researcher', Accessed: 2025-09-23. [Online]. Available: <https://independent.academia.edu/gardnermilo>.
- [22] *Rhind Mathematical Papyrus*, in *Wikipedia*, 2025-08-31. Accessed: 2025-09-23. [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Rhind_Mathematical_Papyrus&oldid=1308748933.
- [23] 'Egyptian Granite Vases Carved with High Precision', Accessed: 2025-09-01. [Online]. Available: <https://ancientlorequest.com/en/articles/egyptian-granite-vases-carved-with-high-precision/>.
- [24] *Younger Dryas*, in *Wikipedia*, 2025-08-20. Accessed: 2025-08-24. [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Younger_Dryas&oldid=1306908953.
- [25] 'Homepage | Taş Tepeler', Accessed: 2025-08-24. [Online]. Available: <https://tastepeler.org/en>.
- [26] 'Obituary information for Hugh Patrick Bannon', Accessed: 2023-09-18. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cremation-society.com/obituaries/obituary-listings?obId=24879300>.
- [27] 'Larry Pahl - Academia.edu', Accessed: 2023-09-18. [Online]. Available: <https://independent.academia.edu/LarryPahl>.
- [28] G. Dormion and N. Grimal, *La chambre de Chéops : analyse architecturale / Gilles Dormion* (Etudes d'égyptologie). Fayard. [Paris], 2004, 311 p.-XVI p. de pl. en noir et en coul. ; ill., plans, couv. ill. en coul. ; 24 cm, ISBN: 978-2-213-62229-3. Accessed: 2025-08-12. [Online]. Available: <https://nicea-bmvr.nice.fr/PATRIMOINE/doc/SYRACUSE/717623/la-chambre-de-cheops-analyse-architecturale-gilles-dormion>.
- [29] 'NEC SecretSymbol Presentation PDF | PDF | Triangle | Geometry', Scribd, Accessed: 2023-09-18. [Online]. Available: <https://www.scribd.com/document/387579376/NEC-SecretSymbol-Presentation-pdf>.